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Research

Article

**UTILITY OF FROZEN SECTION IN OVARIAN CANCERS IN
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Abstract:

Objectives: The basic aim of the study is to analyze the utility of frozen section in ovarian cancers. **Material and methods:** This cross-sectional study was conducted in Nishtar Hospital, Multan during June 2019 to December 2019. This study was conducted with the permission of ethical committee of hospital. The following parameters were noted-age of the patient, size of the tumor, unilateral/bilateral, solid/cystic/solid and cystic. After gross examination, two to five sections were taken depending on the size and heterogeneity of the lesions. Sections of 4–5 microns were taken and rapid hematoxylin and eosin staining was done. After the frozen section analysis tissues were put in formalin and routine processing was done. **Results:** The data were collected from 237 ovarian cancer patients. The age group ranged from 14 to 86 years and the mean age was 46 years. The mean size of the tumors was 14 cm and ranged from 3 to 36 cm. In 29 cases, the lesions were bilateral. The distribution of various ovarian lesions according to permanent section result were as follows–27 nonneoplastic lesions, 153 epithelial tumors, 16 sex cord stromal tumors, 30 germ cell tumors and seven metastatic tumors. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that diagnostic accuracy rate for frozen section analysis is high for benign and malignant ovarian tumors, but remain relatively low for borderline ovarian tumors.

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INTRODUCTION:

Ovarian tumors constitute a heterogeneous group of lesions which include benign, borderline and malignant tumors. A diagnostic tool which helps to identify various ovarian lesions with high degree of accuracy will help the surgeon to choose appropriate operating procedure. Preoperative diagnostic modalities include serum tumor marker level estimation and imaging [1]. The serum tumor marker- CA 125 is not specific. Women with suspected early-stage ovarian cancer need surgical staging which involves taking samples from areas within the abdominal cavity and retroperitoneal lymph nodes in order to inform further treatment [2]. One potential strategy is to surgically stage all women with suspicious ovarian masses, without any histological information during surgery. This avoids incomplete staging, but puts more women at risk of potential surgical over-treatment [3].

A second strategy is to perform a two-stage procedure to remove the pelvic mass and subject it to paraffin sectioning, which involves formal tissue fixing with formalin and paraffin embedding, prior to ultrathin sectioning and multiple site sampling of the tumor [4]. Surgeons may then base further surgical staging on this histology, reducing the rate of over-treatment, but conferring additional surgical and anaesthetic morbidity [5].

A third strategy is to perform a rapid histological analysis on the ovarian mass during surgery, known as 'frozen section' [6]. Tissues are snap frozen to allow fine tissue sections to be cut and basic histochemical staining to be performed. Surgeons can perform or avoid the full surgical staging procedure depending on the results [7].

Aims and objectives

The basic aim of the study is to analyze the utility of frozen section in ovarian cancers.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Table 1: Histological types according to permanent section results

Histopathology Diagnosis	Number	Percentage
Non-neoplastic lesions	27	11.58
Epithelial tumors	153	65.67
Sex cord stromal tumors	16	6.9
Germ cell tumors	30	12.87
Metastasis	7	3

Frozen section examination showed cells arranged in glandular pattern with focal increased cellularity and minimal atypia. The stroma showed focal fibrosis.

This cross-sectional study was conducted in Nishtar Hospital, Multan during June 2019 to December 2019. This study was conducted with the permission of ethical committee of hospital. The following parameters were noted-age of the patient, size of the tumor, unilateral/bilateral, solid/cystic/solid and cystic.

After gross examination, two to five sections were taken depending on the size and heterogeneity of the lesions. Sections of 4–5 microns were taken and rapid hematoxylin and eosin staining was done. After the frozen section analysis tissues were put in formalin and routine processing was done. The results of frozen section diagnosis were compared with the permanent section diagnosis. The lesions included non-neoplastic and neoplastic entities. The neoplastic lesions were categorized into benign, borderline and malignant. The neoplastic lesions included epithelial tumors, germ cell tumors, sex cord stromal tumors and metastatic tumors. The cases which underwent torsion with extensive hemorrhage and infarction were excluded from the study. Overall accuracy was defined as the percentage of concordance between frozen and final diagnosis.

Statistical analysis

The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value and negative predictive value in diagnosing each category were calculated. The cases with diagnostic discrepancies were reviewed and the possible causes of diagnostic errors analyzed.

RESULTS:

The data were collected from 237 ovarian cancer patients. The age group ranged from 14 to 86 years and the mean age was 46 years. The mean size of the tumors was 14 cm and ranged from 3 to 36 cm. In 29 cases, the lesions were bilateral. The distribution of various ovarian lesions according to permanent section result were as follows—27 nonneoplastic lesions, 153 epithelial tumors, 16 sex cord stromal tumors, 30 germ cell tumors and seven metastatic tumors.

Frozen section of ovarian cells

DISCUSSION:

Frozen section examination can diagnose the benign conditions with a high degree of accuracy. Out of 122 cases reported as benign on frozen section analysis, diagnostic discrepancy occurred in four cases [9]. In three cases there were focal borderline areas in addition to the predominant benign component. One case showed a combination of benign, borderline and focal low-grade invasive carcinoma. The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value and negative predictive value of frozen section in diagnosing benign conditions in this study were 99.2, 96.5, 96.72 and 99.1 % respectively [10].

Borderline ovarian tumors constitute 10–20 % of all ovarian malignancies. The borderline ovarian tumors usually occur in younger age group and the long-term prognosis is significantly better. The accurate diagnosis is critical to avoid overtreatment or under treatment. The diagnosis of borderline ovarian tumor in older age group will lead the surgeon to do hysterectomy, bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy and surgical staging [8]. With the same diagnosis in reproductive age group, where the incidence of borderline tumors are high, the surgical management is fertility conserving surgery-unilateral salpingo-oophorectomy or even cystectomy with surgical staging [11].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that diagnostic accuracy rate for frozen section analysis is high for benign and malignant ovarian tumors, but remain relatively low for borderline ovarian tumors. The possible predictive factors affecting false positive or false negative diagnosis should carefully be taken into consideration to reduce the diagnostic discrepancies.

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